

Milestone: M5.2 Maturity level model defined: standards, indicators and review framework

Lead Participant: INSA

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Due: 31 Oct 2021

Date Of Completion: 9 Nov 2021

Means of Verification

- Delphi Round 1 Report to experts: [Delphi Round 1 Report](#)
- Delphi Round 2 Report to experts: [Delphi Round 2 Report](#)
- B1MG MLM Framework: [B1MG MLM Framework](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes. This was due to:

- Delphi panel Experts took longer than expected to provide answers the two survey Rounds;
- After Round 2, there was need to have additional input from some 1+MG WGs to reach the final MLM framework.

Project participants & others

- WP5 Team: Astrid Vicente, Alexandra Costa, Maria Luís Cardoso, Fátima Lopes, mafalda Bourbon, Teresa Caldas Almeida (INSA), Serena Scollen, Melissa Konopko, Arshiya Merchant, Xènia Pèrez Sitjà (ELIXIR), Helen Lepa (Tervise Arengu Instituut), Osvaldo Santos (FMUL)
- Contributions from 1+MG Working Groups, in particular A. Thorogood, R Becker (WG2), I Custer, J Vinikainen, V Relel, L Ake-Levin, P Villari (WG6), J Belien (WG3), I Gut (WG4), T Nyronen (WG5)
- 14 Delphi survey Experts

Next action steps

- Testing the MLM in healthcare systems from pilot countries/regions
- Organize a Workshop on the MLM
- Make the MLM accessible to countries as a tool to assess maturity of their healthcare systems regarding the use of genomics

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